

WAYS OF USING ACTION GAMES AND NON-STANDARD GAME EXERCISES TO IMPROVE BALL CONTROL TRAINING FOR BASKETBALL PLAYERS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, it is important to effectively organize physical education lessons in general secondary schools and to use action games in teaching physical education program sections. Information was also given that the wide use of mobile games has a good effect in the activities of basketball clubs organized in general secondary schools.

Our Honorable President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev is paying special attention to the training of specialists - personnel, teachers and coaches who are able to take people from mass sports to the heights of professional sports. "Strategy of Actions" designed to implement the five priority areas of development by the President in 2017-2021, five important initiatives of the President introduced in the social and spiritual-educational sphere, June 3, 2017 "Physical education and Decision No. PQ-3031 on measures for the further development of mass sports, PF-5368 of March 5, 2018 "On measures to fundamentally improve the state management system in the field of physical education and sports" - is being formed within the framework of the requirements of the Decree No. 1 and other similar conceptual documents. It will help to raise comprehensive work on training young people in the physical and patriotic spirit, preparing them for military service to a new level, and to regularly fill their interest in sports with new talented young people. The winners discovered in the competitions will be involved in the national teams of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In Uzbekistan, the country becomes the priority direction of social and economic development.

It is important to effectively organize physical education lessons in general secondary schools and to use action games in teaching physical education program sections. Also, the wide use of mobile games in the activities of sports clubs organized in general secondary schools has a good effect.

The experience of using action games and non-standard game exercises in improving the training of ball control techniques in basketball games of the participants in the basketball sports club organized in general secondary schools was studied.

During this experiment, during the training of control and research groups consisting of students participating in basketball sports circles, the above test and control exercises were

added in the form of non-standard game exercises and action games to improve the physical fitness of students and basketball. In the game, effective improvement of movement skills and skills in ball control techniques was studied.

In addition to test control exercises, we used the following action games during training.

- Who passes the most balls in 30 seconds.
- jump and throw the ball in two steps.
- Fighting for the ball.
- Relay free throw.
- Swift-footed teams.
- To the neighbors.
- Passing balls.
- Drop the ball into the basket.
- Dropping the ball into the basket or basket.
- The relay of carrying the ball and throwing it into the basket.
- Relay of basketball players.
- Aiming the ball at the target.

Action games. It is a complex activity consisting of various emotional movements. This activity is performed in conditions and tasks that suddenly change based on established rules.

Action games differ from other physical exercises in terms of organizing and managing the activities of those who do it. During the game, there is a need to act in suddenly changing situations and to solve movement tasks in a short period of time, showing physical qualities such as quickness and agility.

It strengthens motor skills. During the game, children's activities are organized on the basis of figurative, plot and game tasks, and in order to perform them for a long time, they evoke positive emotions so that they can perform them with enthusiasm. This, in turn, strengthens the effect on their body, helps to develop their physical qualities.

Adherence to the rules of the game creates mutually reinforcing behavior, moral virtues are mutually supportive. Game activity is a combination of various actions with a complex character.

In the physical education of schoolchildren, it is envisaged to implement the tasks of health promotion, education and upbringing. Through action games, there are more opportunities to complete these tasks as a whole.

Health tasks. The main task of physical education of 6-8 graders is to protect the child's life and strengthen his health, to protect himself by training his body and to increase resistance to various diseases, to withstand unfavorable conditions of the external environment. is to teach. In addition, it is very important to increase the ability to work in children. Since the development of the child's organism has its own characteristics, its tasks are expressed in a more precise form: help to the smooth and timely hardening of the child's bones, the formation of curved areas in the back spine, good development of the surface of the heel, maturation of the ligaments. show (games); proper development of body parts is made possible (games); develops all muscle groups. It is also necessary to make it possible to improve the activity of the cardiovascular system: to increase the flow of blood to the heart, to improve the normal functioning of the heart and to develop its ability to adapt to an

unexpectedly changed load; increase the mobility of the chest, ensure deep breathing and long-term stability of this activity, increase the vital capacity of the lungs, improve breathing through the nose, correct internal organs ensuring the functioning of the brain, improving the central nervous system; it is necessary to ensure that the mobility of the states of excitement and inhibition is at the same level, as well as to perfect the motor analyzer and sensory organs. The level of functionality of a young organism allows use in the size and intensity of the load.

Educational tasks. It is also important to perform educational tasks in the process of conducting national folk games with 6-8-year-old students. These tasks include: formation of movement skills and abilities, development of physical qualities (agility, speed, endurance, balance, dexterity, strength, endurance), proper body posture, assimilation of knowledge about physical education. Due to the flexibility of the nervous system, movement skills are formed in children more easily than in adults. Many of these skills (walking, running, jumping) are used by children as means of movement in everyday life. Movement skills facilitate the child's communication with the environment and help him perceive it.

Information about the knowledge directly related to physical culture for primary school students (useful side of games, importance and technical performance of physical training, methods of their performance, rules of folk national games, etc.) providing information is of great importance. The deeper the knowledge that students have, the more intelligently they can use folk games, the more effectively they can engage in games, and the more they can independently use physical culture tools in the school and family environment.

Educational tasks. Engage in physical culture, inculcate in children the habit of observing the established order and the desire to engage in folk games regularly every day if possible, and let them engage in this game independently at school and at home. It is necessary to develop the ability to receive, to organize games in the group of children of their age and younger than themselves, to teach them to perform them together. It is necessary to educate students to look at national games with love, with interest in the results of these games, and with envy at the victories achieved by athletes.

In the process of learning games, there are great opportunities for moral, intellectual, aesthetic and cocktail education. Positive (cooperation, discipline, humility, kindness) and moral qualities (honesty, justice, sense of friendship, cooperation, ability to work in sync with the times, ability to complete tasks) in children's behavior while performing folk games. "responsibility", as well as the best conditions and opportunities for the manifestation of willpower (courage, determination, confidence in one's own strength, steadfastly overcoming difficulties, endurance, etc.).

In short, the goals, tasks, and development of the basketball sports clubs organized in secondary schools for the development of physical education, physical fitness, and physical qualities of students, and the improvement of the methodology for teaching the ball control technique of basketball players. The successful implementation of the methods can be seen in the research results.

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